

DEMAX Proposal 994423: Certificate of Analysis (CoA)

Date: 24 May 2022

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Molecule(s) requested: 50g wet cell paste, containing deuterated myoglobin (pLEICS03)

Cell type: *E. coli* strain BL21 Tuner DE3

Selection: Kanamycin

Additives: Hemin

Deuterated carbon source: d8-glycerol, d-algae extract prepared in-house from *Botryococcus braunii*

Expected level of deuteration: Between 96-99%

Yield: 67 g of wet cell paste provided in 6 x 50 mL tubes (10-11g in each). Cells contain deuterated myoglobin (expressed from pLEICS03 provided proposer).

SDS-PAGE (Biorad Mini-Protean TGX, Any kD):

Lane 1: PageRuler Prestained (Thermofisher) (5 uL)

Lane 2: blank

Lane 3: Whole cells at time of induction, 0 hours (15 uL)

Lane 4: blank

Lane 5: Whole cells at time of harvest, after 18 hours induction (15 uL)

